

On the Origin of the lunar sulfur – revisiting S isotope fractionation during lunar core formation

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Abstract

Sulfur isotopes provide key constraints on the origin and evolution of volatiles in rocky planets. The terrestrial mantle is isotopically lighter in sulfur than its potential chondritic precursors, whereas the lunar mantle displays systematically heavier $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values. Understanding the origin of this difference within the Earth–Moon system is essential for reconstructing volatile behavior during planetary differentiation and the formation of the Moon.

Because sulfur is moderately siderophile, metal–silicate segregation during planetary core formation has long been considered a potential driver of sulfur isotope fractionation. However, experimental constraints on sulfur isotope fractionation during metal–silicate segregation remain limited and are largely restricted to sulfur-saturated conditions. Here we present new high-pressure, high-temperature experiments quantifying sulfur isotope fractionation between metal and silicate under S-undersaturated conditions relevant to magma-ocean differentiation. Our results reveal systematically negative fractionations between metal and silicate ($\Delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{met-sil}} = -1.1 \pm 0.1$ to -2.3 ± 0.1 ‰) in Fe–Ni alloys, which become more negative under increasingly reducing conditions and depend strongly on metal composition (Si and Ni contents), oxygen fugacity, and temperature (1500–1900 °C). These results contrast with previous experiments performed under S-saturated conditions, where small positive fractionations were reported.

Despite these large fractionations, metal–silicate segregation during Earth’s core formation cannot reproduce the light $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ signature of the present-day mantle, indicating that additional processes, possibly evaporation at the surface of its magma ocean, must have modified Earth’s mantle S isotope composition. By contrast, modeling of lunar core formation under lunar magma ocean conditions shows that the $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ composition of the lunar mantle can be reproduced if the Moon inherited its sulfur inventory from the terrestrial magma ocean. This result implies that the S isotopic composition of Earth’s mantle has remained broadly stable since the Moon-forming impact.